

MBS Hedge Ratio

Investment-banking statistical-research working paper

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Hedge Ratio for Mortgage-Backed Securities*

I. Purpose

This memo summarizes my research on the approach of using Treasury bond futures contracts to hedge long positions in mortgage-backed securities (MBS). This research was to be used as a building block for a customer-oriented (rather than MHT trading) product which would specify the proper hedge ratio and futures position for any MBS as a function of such observable variables as the coupon rate of the MBS pool, the current market mortgage rate, and the current slope of the money market yield curve.

Based on my findings, however, I have reached the conclusion that such a product would be **ill-advised**, due to the sizable errors to which the hedge ratio would be subjected, even using the best (i.e. most statistically significant) model. My recommendation is that mortgage-backed securities hedges for customers be implemented and managed on an ad hoc basis by our marketing people, and **that we discontinue efforts to produce a specific product for this purpose.**

* Executive memorandum, dated June 25, 1986, written by **John D. Pappas** at Manufacturers Hanover Trust, predecessor bank of JPMorgan. The statistical analysis outlined herein was carried out in the headquarters of the bank and later of JPMorgan—270 Park Ave., New York (cover photo)—under the supervision of **Carl A. Batlin**, Vice President of the bank, and **Donald H. Layton**, then Senior Managing Director of the Swaps and Futures Group of the bank's Investment Banking Division, and later Vice-Chairman of JPMorgan.

II. A Model of the Hedge Ratio

Normally, a standard approach for estimating the appropriate hedge ratio with which to hedge a cash market instrument (e.g. MBS) with futures is to perform a linear regression of price changes in the cash market instrument against price changes in the futures contract. Since the slope coefficient represents the volatility of the futures relative to cash, it serves as an estimate of the hedge ratio.

In the case of MBS, however, using this methodology is complicated by the fact that MBS contains an implicit prepayment option which can be exercised at the ultimate discretion of the mortgagor. Accordingly, when option exercise is considered more likely, market perceptions of the MBS duration fall, MBS volatility declines, and the appropriate hedge ratio is therefore reduced.

This phenomenon can be taken into account with a two-stage regression procedure: First, I segmented the data (3 years of daily data) into small subperiods and run the original regression in each subperiod. Then, I performed a second regression for which each subperiod represented one observation. The hedge ratio was the dependent variable, and observable variables which determine the probability of option exercise were the independent variables. Since the value of the hedge ratio can be produced instantaneously based on currently observable independent variables, the appropriate hedge can be implemented in a timely fashion.

This is in contrast to other approaches, which update hedge ratios by re-running the original regression over the most recent time period;

by the time the use adjusts the hedge using such a method, a loss has already been incurred from having the wrong hedge ratio in place.

III. Outline of the Statistical Method

To implement the two-stage approach, I first needed to segment the data into subperiods. The subperiods needed to be large enough to produce good estimates of the individual hedge ratios, but not so large as to leave an insufficient number of observation for performing a meaningful second-stage regression. I chose 40 observations per subperiod as a number which balanced these considerations.

Next, I needed to specify the independent variables against which to regress the hedge ratios. I settled to three factors which affect the probability of option exercise. First, the degree to which the option is in or out of the money, as measured by the **spread** between the market mortgage rate and the coupon rate of the MBS, should be of paramount importance. I chose to run a separate regression for each coupon pool, permitting me to use the average subperiod GNMA yield for the coupon pool as an independent variable for each of the second-stage regressions, rather than the spread itself. Second, **skewness** in interest rate movements should be important, since when rates are likely to rise (fall), the prepayment option is less (more) likely to be exercised. I experimented with the slope of the Eurodollar yield curve (i.e. 6-month LIBOR minus 3-month LIBOR), the spread between the implied Eurodollar futures rate and 3-month LIBOR, and the recent change in interest rates as possible proxies for the skewness effect. Finally, high **variance** of interest

rate changes should make an in-the-money (out-of-the-money) option less (more) likely to be exercised. The problem with variance as an independent variable is that it is not directly observable and there are no good proxies to measure it. I included the subperiod variance of GNMA yield changes as an independent variable anyway, though, to see if it would improve the statistical properties of the second-stage regression.

IV. Statistical Results

Hedge ratio series were constructed for 6 GNMA coupon pools (8%, 9%, 11.5%, 14%, and 15%) and second-stage regressions were run for each pool. Skewness proxies failed to be statistically significant and were therefore omitted. The attached table gives the results of the hedge ratio equations as a function of the average GNMA yield and the variance of GNMA yield changes.

In general, the equations for the low coupon pools had low explanatory power and therefore could not be used to produce reliable hedge ratios. While the equations for the higher coupon pools were better, they still left large room for prediction error. Moreover, high coupons had prepayment options which are currently deep in-the-money, since market rates have fallen substantially. As a result, predicted and actual hedge ratios tend toward zero, since the MBS behaves more like a money market instrument and cannot therefore be hedged effectively with Treasury bond futures. Thus, the statistical results suggest that **it does not appear to be possible to use this approach to hedge MBS.**

HEDGE RATIO FOR MORGAGE-BACKED SECURITIES

<p>Regression: $HR_i = a_0 + a_1 \bar{R}_i + a_2 \text{Var}[\Delta R]_i$</p> <p>$HR_i$: Optimal hedge-ratio in subperiod i.</p> <p>\bar{R}_i : Average annualized yield of GNMA security in subperiod i.</p> <p>$\text{Var}[\Delta R]_i$: Variance of daily GNMA security in subperiod i.</p>							
GNMA COUPON	Coefficients			Statistics			
	a_0	a_1	a_2	F_1	R^2	DW**	P
8.0%	+	0.0487* (10.1)	8.319* (2.5)	5.27	0.291	1.71	0.421 (2.2)
9.0%	+	0.053* (18.3)	2.203 (1.5)	7.13	0.353	1.73	0.287 (1.5)
11.5%		-0.341 (-1.3)	0.086* (2.3)	20.44* (2.4)	10.34	0.443	1.82 (2.0)
13.0%		-2.51* (-4.7)	0.24* (5.6)	5.3* (2.0)	24.30	0.643	2.07 -
14.0%		-1.91 (-1.9)	0.22* (2.0)	30.0* (2.7)	9.56	0.424	1.93 (1.5)
15.0%		-2.00* (-4.1)	0.26* (4.4)	6.5 (1.1)	13.66	0.512	2.04 (2.3)
<p>* Statistically significant at the 95% level; t-statistics are reported in parentheses below the coefficients.</p> <p>** After correction for first-order autocorrelation (except for the 13% coupon).</p> <p>+ Constant suppressed due to extremely low significance.</p>							

STATISTICAL ADDENDUM

A. Theoretical review and outline of parameters used in the analysis

The Practice of cross-hedging mortgage-backed securities (MBS) with Treasury bond futures contracts has the characteristic that MBS implicitly contains a call option which may be exercised when the market mortgage rate falls below the coupon rate.

For a given short period, the appropriate hedge-ratio that minimizes the variance of the gain or loss from the hedged position can be specified by regressing the differences in the MBS prices (P_m) against the differences in the Treasury futures prices (P_t) in the period: $P_m = \mathbf{b}P_t + \mathbf{e}$.

The regression coefficient (\mathbf{b}) has the property of minimizing the variance of the residuals [$\text{Var}(\mathbf{e})$] which is equal to the variance of the gain or loss from the hedged position [$\text{Var}(P_m - \mathbf{b}P_t)$]. It is obvious that the hedge-ratio, thus specified, depends on the variability (and covariance) of the changes in the MBS and Treasury futures prices. These changes are a function of the yield and the duration of each security. The peculiar characteristic of the MBS (the implied call option) entails a random element in the duration of the security which, in turn, affects the optimal hedge-ratio.

Therefore, over a long period, the optimal hedge-ratio will change, as the duration of the MBS changes making the price of the security

more (less) sensitive to changes in the interest rates, relatively to the sensitivity of Treasury futures prices, if the duration of the MBS increases (decreases). Since the duration in the mortgage-backed security is affected, due to the implicit prepayment option, by the market mortgage rates, the optimal hedge-ratio could be specified from information that is relevant to the market mortgage rates and is encapsured in the following three variables:

- a) The **spread** ($r_m - c_m$) between the market mortgage rate (r_m) and the coupon rate (c_m) measuring the degree to which the prepayment option is currently in or out of the money. When the option is in the money, i.e. when the exercise of the prepayment option is more likely, the duration of the MBS is reduced. The result is a decline in the systematic volatility of the MBS price relatively to the volatility of the Treasury futures price and, consequently, a rather consistent lowering in the optimal hedge ratio. When the option is out of the money, the effects are diametrically opposite.

- b) The **variance** in the market mortgage rates. When the prepayment option is out of the money, a higher variance increases the likelihood that the spread between the MBS market and coupon rates becomes negative in the future and therefore increases the probability that the prepayment option will be exercised, resulting in the lowering in the hedge-ratio. When the option is in the money, the higher the variance the higher the probability that the market mortgage rate will exceed the contractual rate in the future, raising the optimal hedge ratio. In conclusion, the variance in the market mortgage rate is related to the optimal hedge-ratio negatively when the market

rate exceeds the coupon rate of the MBS pool, and positively when it falls short of the coupon rate.

- c) The **skewness** in the probability distribution of changes in the mortgage rates which takes positive values when rising mortgage rates are more likely and negative values in the opposite case. The importance of the skewness in determining the optimal hedge-ratio is theoretically attributed to the fact that when falling market mortgage rates are more likely, the probability that the prepayment option will be exercised increases, reducing the duration of the MBS and lowering the hedge-ratio.

C. Data segmentation and 2-step regressions

A 2-step regression procedure was implemented whereby the output of the first regression was used as input (dependent variable) of the second regression:

- **Step 1.** For each coupon, a time series of “optimal” hedge-ratios was created. The data (concerning the MBS and T-bond futures prices) were segmented into subsets and the first differences in the MBS prices were regressed against the first differences in the T-bond futures prices. The regression coefficient corresponding to each subset constitutes the optimal hedge-ratio for the subperiod.

As to the data-segmentation method, since the optimal hedge-ratio is a function of other variables (market mortgage rates, skewness etc.), the regression equation used in Step 1 ($P_m = bP_t + e$) can be viewed as a piecewise regression model

with joint points of structural change and deterministic switching on the basis of other variables. Ideally, from a purely theoretical perspective, the points of structural change should be identified using *ex ante* criteria (like different levels or/and variance of interest rates), and the segmentation scheme should be tested for the null hypothesis of no separate regimes along the lines of Goldfeld and Quandt (1973).

However, since we are dealing with any types of mortgage-backed securities (with different coupons), this tedious procedure would be costly and inefficient in its application. Therefore a second-best alternative was implemented by segmenting the data in many small subsets of fixed size, with the purpose of approximating the behavior of the hedge-ratio in each (large) structurally homogenous period by the behavior of the hedge-ratio in many (small) fixed-size subperiods derived by segmenting the period. This concept was implemented by designing an algorithm which generates different segmentation schemes (i.e. different subset size and different starting data position of the segmentation procedure in each run) running many regressions (of the order of thousands) in very limited computer time (of the order of minutes)

Moreover, it should be pointed out that a serious trade-off in this procedure exists, on the basis of subset size, between the percentage of explained variation in changes of the MBS prices derived from information concerning changes in the T-bond prices (i.e. the value of R^2 in the regression $P_m = \mathbf{b}P_t + \mathbf{e}$) and the explained variation in the hedge ratio derived from information concerning the interest rates [i.e. the value of R^2 in the regression $b_i = a_0 + a_1r_{m,i} + a_2\text{Var}(r_m) + \dots$]. A higher subset size would entail a lower value of the former and a higher value

of the latter, and vice versa. Although a criterion for the “optimal” subset size can easily be specified, varying the subset size does not affect the qualitative results of this analysis.

- **Step 2.** For each subset, the following variables were calculated:
 - (a) The average value of the MBS annualized yield.
 - (b) The variance of the first difference in the MBS yield.
 - (c) The average difference between the 3-month and 1-month LIBOR deposit rate.
 - (d) The difference between the average MBS yield in the last week of the subperiod and the average yield in the first week of the subperiod.

The last two variables were used as proxy variables for the skewness in the probability distribution of r_m . The regression coefficients (“optimal” hedge-ratios) from Step 1 were regressed against these four variables.

D. Regression results

The four most important results of the outlined 2-step regression analysis are the following:

- 1) Although data analysis validated the theoretical contention that the optimal hedge ratio depends on the level and variance of the market mortgage rates, this relationship is not strong enough to guarantee a successful cross-hedge of the MBS with T-bond

futures contracts. As it is outlined in the table (p. 6), although there is a statistically significant relation between the optimal hedge-ratio and the level and variability of the market mortgage rate (significant **t** and **F** statistics), the impact of changes in the level of the variance of this rate do not account for a large fraction of the variability in the optimal hedge-ratio (relative low value of the R^2 statistic). Correlation analysis gives equivalent results.

- 2) A relatively good fit between the optimal hedge-ratio and the level and variability of the market mortgage rates is obtained only when the spread between the MBS market yield and its coupon rate is negative. The reason is that a negative value of the spread has a direct strong impact on the expected price sensitivity of the prepayment option and, consequently, on the stability of the relation between MBS and the Treasury futures contracts. However, when the prepayment option is far out of the money, changes in the level and variance of the interest rate become less determinate (even less determinate than the theory would anticipate) of relative changes in the MBS and T-bond prices, since the likelihood that the prepayment option will be exercised is smaller. Because of this fact, the strategy of cross-hedging low-coupon MBS with Treasury futures contracts is **highly risky** and **its success dubious**. On the other hand, it would make little sense, from a marketing point of view, to attempt to hedge only high coupon MBS while avoiding hedging low-coupons ones, on the grounds that we get good and theoretically consistent results only in the case of the former ones.

- 2) The two proxy variables that were used to approximate the effect of skewness in the probability distribution to r_m , statistically have

proven to be less significant than the theory contends for skewness. Therefore they were excluded from the model, as it is specified on the table (p. 6). It is a possibility though that there exist other appropriate proxy variables for skewness that still have to be identified. However, given the results as to the other variables affecting the optimal hedge-ratio, further research might be justified only if the profit margins from a cross-hedging product of this type were considered high.

- 4) Caution should be made against the certainty of measurement errors, which is inherent in the model. Specifically, the variance in the market mortgage rates would have to be approximated by using either proxy variables or past experience on the behavior of the variance or a combination of both. This approach would accentuate the problem analyzed above.

D. Concluding recommendation

Taking into consideration (a) the limited potential of the available theoretical framework in specifying in an accurate and marketable way the optimal hedge-ratio from information pertaining to the interest rates, (b) the statistical problems inherent in specifying and using the appropriate model for determining this ratio, and (c) the limited profit margin that is anticipated from marketing this product on a commission basis, it is hereby recommended that **any further research should be discontinued** in this direction since it may be considered **prohibitive** on a cost-benefit basis.